

MATERNAL HEALTH IN RURAL KARNATAKA

Abstract

Stable, steady, secured health status of women is an integral part of overall health system. It is imperative to note that stable health of women may not be some time secured and steady. These three aspects are essential components of women's health. Among other things, reproductive health is an essential status of every woman. Usually women undergo most of the health complications especially during their reproductive and post-reproductive stage. In recent times issues pertaining to the reproductive health status of women have gained momentum especially after Cairo conference (1992). It is sad to note that for most health complications women themselves are not directly responsible. Socio-cultural factors mostly responsible for poor reproductive level of women in India. Desire for male child, unmet family planning desires, poor maternal care, place of delivery are some the major factors influence women's reproductive health. Rural women in India are the worst sufferers. They share the major burden of poor maternal care, low level of education, early marriage and higher levels of fertility. This paper throws light on the maternal health status of rural women of Karnataka. This study is based on secondary data.

Introduction

Health is an important aspect of every living being on this earth. Every human being is struggling hard to maintain and sustain health and well being. However stable foundation and growth of every society and community always depends on the concrete health status of women. 'If women are inadequately nourished- as are, about half the women in most of it limits their physical development, compromises their health and threatens their ability to bear healthy children. Malnourished women are sick; more have smaller babies and die earlier. And where infant and child mortality is high, birth rates are also high-increasing the stress on women's bodies and tapping them and their children in a cycle of poor health and nutrition (The World's Women 2010).

It is distressing that women throughout their lives have unequal access to health – care systems and services relative to men. Health conditions in one phase of a woman's life affect other phases of her life as well. This concept guided the Technical Discussions on Women, Health and Development at the 45th World Health Assembly in 1992. Since then, WHO has advocated strongly for lifespan approach to women's health –from conception to old-age. It has also called for multicultural action for women's health, particularly in the areas of raising female literacy, creating opportunities for income generation, increasing the participation of women in national development, and in short , empowering women to make decisions on matters that impact their health.

In recent times there is a growing realization that investing in women's health is investing in the health of families, communities and societies, in other words-investing in health for all. It is important to note that health is both an important factor in the achievement of status as well as an indicator of social status, particularly for women, whose health is conditioned to a great extent by social attitudes. The health status of women includes their mental and social condition, which are affected by prevailing norms and attitudes of society in addition to their biological and psychological problems. Societies delineate women's roles partly according to their biological functions and partly from prevailing attitudes regarding their physical and mental capacity. These social attitudes also influence the provision and use of preventive and curative healthcare, including maternal care. The healthcare facilities offered by a community in the form of medical particularly maternity services for women is a significant index of the emphasis that community places on the health of its women. Some studies in both the developed and developing countries have shown a definite link between low status of women

and deficiencies in the knowledge and utilization of preventive health services. (S.L. Goel 2008).

One of the most major issues which are affecting the health status of women is their reproductive health. Importance of reproductive health status has gained momentum after The International Conference on Population and Development Programme of Action (1992). This conference stressed on the holistic approach towards women's health. There was an effort to look women's health from socio-economic and cultural perspectives. It is important to note that a reproductive health approach would differ from a narrow family planning approach in several ways. Family planning programmes were largely determined by a demographic imperative, without due consideration to related health issues such as maternal health or STD (sexually transmitted diseases) prevention and management. Evaluation of the programme was largely in terms of quantity rather than quality. In general, such programmes exclusively targeted women, taking little account of the social, cultural and intimate realities of their reproductive lives and decision-making powers. They tended to serve only married people, excluding, in particular, young people. But reproductive health approach would aim to build upon what exists and at the same time to modify current narrow, vertical programmes to ones in which every opportunity is taken to offer women and men a full range of reproductive health services in a linked way. We all know that in a country like India, women bear the burden of reproductive health problems. They are at risk of complications from pregnancy and childbirth. They also face risks in preventing unwanted pregnancy, suffer the complications of unsafe abortion, bear most of the burden of contraception, and are more exposed to contracting, and suffering the complications of reproductive tract infection (RTI's), particularly sexually transmitted diseases (STDs). Among women of reproductive age, a considerable part of their healthy years of life lost is due to reproductive health problems such as unregulated fertility, maternal mortality and morbidity and sexually transmitted diseases including HIV/AIDS. The overall burden of reproductive ill health is very high and many women die every year due to the complications of pregnancy and child birth. Maternal mortality which continues to remain unacceptably high glaringly reflects the inequity in women's access to basic life saving interventions as well as inadequacy of the health care system. Most maternal deaths occur due to haemorrhage, sepsis, toxemia, obstructed labour and unsafe abortions while safe and affordable technologies to prevent such deaths do exist. Equally important issues related to this are nutritional anaemia, adolescent pregnancies, and gender discrimination. The high population growth over-shadowing the health gains as

reflected by increase in life expectancy and impressive decline in infant mortality, has resulted in increased demand on the already over stretched health care delivery system.

In this background a study has been made to examine the reproductive health status of rural women of Karnataka. This study is based only on secondary sources like NFHS and DLHS. In most developing countries, such as India, utilization of basic health services has remained poor even though there has been increasing public and private expenditure on the provision of advanced health care. The low utilization seems to be due to low levels of household income, high illiteracy and ignorance, and a host of traditional factors. On the other hand, despite substantial public investments in health infrastructure the supply of such services continues to be inadequate and of poor quality.

This paper discusses the issues associated with the requirement of maternal health care services and provides an analysis of the determinants of the use of reproductive health care services associated with pregnancy and child delivery by women in rural Karnataka. More specifically this paper analyses some important aspects of maternal health. They are Fertility Rate, Teenage pregnancy and motherhood, Mean age at effective marriage of females, Need for family planning, antenatal care, Place of delivery and Assistance during delivery and Maternal Mortality ratio.

FERTILITY RATE

In all societies women not only give birth to the children, but they also do the most of the child care. Therefore situations of high fertility tend them to lock up within the domestic field. In high fertility societies women's relatively short lives were and in some places still are dominated by responsibilities of childbirth and childcare. The recent fertility rate in many developing countries is increasingly getting more attention. The data reveals in Table 1 that fertility in all the age groups is higher in rural areas than in urban areas. The fertility reaches the peak in the age group 20-24 and declines thereafter, irrespective of the place of their residence. More women are focusing on their careers and are marrying late. The very process of planning a baby is delayed. From the age of 32, the ability to conceive per monthly cycle decreases gradually and goes down rapidly after 37. This shows a decrease in the egg quality and lack of sexual activity which is also a contributing factor in declining fertility. In women the causes of infertility includes tubal disease, hereditary abnormalities, and sexual dysfunction or unexplained factors.

Table 1 Rural and Urban Fertility Rate in Karnataka

Age-specific and total fertility rates and crude birth rates from NFHS-3, NFHS-2 and NFHS-1 by residence, Karnataka, 2005-06						
Age	NFHS- III		NFHS-II		NFHS- I	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
15-19	0.052	0.107	0.069	0.135	0.094	0.147
20-24	0.167	0.179	0.160	0.180	0.169	0.226
25-29	0.104	0.099	0.091	0.089	0.127	0.138
30-34	0.040	0.040	0.042	0.033	0.057	0.069
35-39	0.009	0.011	0.010	0.009	0.020	0.026
40-44	0.005	0.001	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.009
45-49	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.009	0.002
TFR 15-44	1.89	2.19	1.89	2.24	2.34	3.07
TFR 15-49	1.89	2.19	1.89	2.25	2.39	3.09
CBR	18.6	20.2	18.5	21.4	22.7	27.5

TFR = Total fertility rate
CBR = Crude birth rate

Source: NFHS-3, 2005-06

TEENAGE PREGNANCY AND MOTHERHOOD

In India, marriage at an early age is still common and unfortunately institutions do not provide any education regarding safe motherhood. The period of adolescence for a girl is a period of physical and psychological preparation for safe motherhood. Early marriages and early pregnancy are acknowledged as cultural norms of our society. But nowadays Teenage Pregnancy is emerging as a serious problem all over the world and more in the developing countries like India. Pregnancy in every young woman is generally considered to be a very high risk event, because teenage girls are physically and psychologically immature for reproduction. Even today teenage pregnancy and motherhood is prevalent in Karnataka, most of the girls in northern parts of rural Karnataka marry within the legal age of marriage. According to the NFHS report 15.7 per cent girls of rural Karnataka marry between the age group of 15 to 19. It is cleared from the report that a majority of teenage pregnant mothers were illiterate. Even though Karnataka state having second highest percentage of mothers in the 15-19 years, because of early marriages, lack of sex education and sexual assault are considered as chief causes for motherhood among underage girls in the state. Teenage may constitute high risk group in reproductive terms because of assumed double burden of reproduction and growth.(Table 2).

MEAN AGE AT EFFECTIVE MARRIAGE OF FEMALES

There is a large evidence to suggest that early child bearing is on the increase everywhere. It presents a serious problem in many countries. As early marriages are prevalent in Indian community, the minimum legal age of marriage for girls in India is 18 years, even then the problem of teenage pregnancy is widespread. In the Indian context, adolescent girls enter into reproductive life, with early life marriage, pregnancies and child bearing resulting in negative effects to their general and reproductive health. A young married woman in India has been increased in which, early marriage may limit young women's lives and compromise their reproductive health and choices. Age at marriage was associated with marital relationship. Young women, who had married late, communicate with their husbands on all reproductive topics like when or whether to have children, how many children to have and to use contraceptive. Likewise, young women who had married early were considerably less than those who had married later, having interactions with their husband.

Background characteristic	Have had a live birth	Are pregnant with first child	Percentage who have begun childbearing	Number of women
Age				
15	4.6	1.1	5.7	171
16	4.6	3.5	8.1	228
17	7.9	3.8	11.7	235
18	17.8	6.3	24.1	280
19	26.7	5.5	32.2	215
Residence				
Urban	8.4	3.0	11.4	457
Rural	15.7	5.1	20.9	672
Education				
No education	35.4	7.6	43.0	158
<5 years complete	22.1	3.4	25.4	57
5-9years complete	12.5	4.6	17.1	444
10 or more years complete	4.2	3.0	7.2	470
Marital status				
Never married	0.0	0.0	0.0	828
Currently married	47.9	16.4	64.4	294
Widowed/divorced/separated/deserted	----	----	----	6
Religion				
Hindu	13.2	4.2	17.4	945
Muslim	10.5	6.3	16.7	143
Christian	3.5	0.0	3.5	31

Others	----	----	----	10
Caste/tribes				
Scheduled castes	17.0	3.8	20.8	185
Scheduled tribes	23.3	3.7	27.0	81
Other backward class	11.9	4.5	16.5	658
Others	7.3	4.3	11.6	155
Wealth index				
Lowest	27.7	7.1	34.9	96
Second	19.2	3.2	22.4	244
Middle	9.7	5.4	15.1	293
Fourth	11.5	5.1	16.6	270
Highest	4.9	1.8	6.7	226

Table 2 Teenage pregnancy and motherhood

Source: NFHS-3, 2005-06

Table 3 Mean age at effective marriage of females, by residence- India and Karnataka, 2006 to 2011

Sl. No.	India & Karnataka	years	Total				Rural				Urban			
			<18	18-20	21+	All Ages	<18	18-20	21+	All Ages	<18	18-20	21+	All Ages
1	India	2006	16.3	19.0	24.1	20.5	16.3	19.0	23.7	20.0	16.3	19.1	24.8	22.0
		2007	16.4	19.0	24.1	20.6	16.3	19.0	23.6	20.0	16.4	19.1	24.9	22.2
		2008	16.3	19.0	23.9	20.7	16.3	19.0	23.5	20.2	16.3	19.2	24.4	22.1
		2009	16.3	19.0	23.9	20.7	16.3	19.0	23.6	20.2	16.5	19.2	24.5	22.2
		2010	16.4	19.1	23.9	21.0	16.4	19.1	23.5	20.5	16.4	19.2	24.6	22.4
		2011	16.5	19.1	23.6	21.2	16.5	19.1	23.3	20.7	16.4	19.3	24.2	22.7
2	Karnataka	2006	16.4	18.9	23.3	20.1	16.4	18.9	23.2	19.8	16.3	19.0	23.5	20.9
		2007	16.4	18.9	23.8	20.3	16.4	18.9	23.4	19.8	16.6	18.9	24.1	21.3
		2008	16.2	18.9	23.7	20.4	16.2	18.9	23.3	19.8	16.1	18.9	24.1	21.4
		2009	16.4	18.9	23.7	20.6	16.4	18.9	23.3	20.0	16.6	18.9	24.2	21.7
		2010	16.5	19.1	23.6	21.1	16.5	19.1	23.2	20.5	16.6	19.3	24.2	22.2
		2011	16.5	19.1	23.6	21	16.6	19	23.2	20.6	16.5	19.7	24.2	21.9

Source: Sample Registration System, Registrar General, India

Table 4 Mean age of marriage in Indian States 2006-2011

Sl. No.	India/Major States	Rural						Urban					
		2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
	India	20.0	20.0	20.2	20.2	20.5	20.7	22.0	22.2	22.1	22.2	22.4	22.7
1	Andhra Pradesh	19.2	19.2	19.7	19.5	20.0	20	20.6	20.4	21.0	20.9	21.7	27.7
2	Assam	21.7	20.3	20.8	20.7	21.1	21.2	23.8	22.9	23.4	23.8	24.5	23.3
3	Bihar	19.2	19.4	19.6	19.9	20.5	20.5	24.6	20.8	22.0	21.2	21.9	21.9
4	Chhattisgarh	19.4	19.8	20.0	20.4	20.1	19.9	21.4	22.0	21.8	23.2	24.3	21.9
5	Delhi	20.8	22.1	21.0	21.4	22.3	21.7	22.1	22.1	22.3	22.6	22.8	22.6
6	Gujarat	20.0	20.5	20.2	20.4	20.4	20.7	22.0	21.6	22.1	21.7	22.0	22.3
7	Haryana	19.9	19.7	20.0	20.2	20.3	20.7	21.1	21.1	20.9	21.6	21.4	21.7
8	Himachal Pradesh	21.6	22.0	21.7	22.1	22.0	22.2	23.3	22.7	22.6	23.9	24.8	24.1
9	Jammu & Kashmir	23.2	23.0	23.5	23.3	23.4	23.8	24.1	24.3	25.5	24.7	25.0	25.4
10	Jharkhand	19.1	20.1	19.9	19.4	19.7	20.3	21.0	21.9	22.0	22.7	22.6	22.7
11	Karnataka	19.8	19.8	19.8	20.0	20.5	20.6	20.9	21.3	21.4	21.7	22.2	21.9
12	Kerala	22.5	22.8	22.5	22.8	22.6	22.6	22.7	22.8	23.2	22.7	22.6	22.8
13	Madhya Pradesh	19.5	19.9	20.1	20.2	20.1	20.1	22.1	25.3	23.0	23.9	22.6	22.7
14	Maharashtra	19.3	19.4	19.5	19.7	19.8	20.7	22.1	23.4	22.0	21.9	22.7	22.5
15	Odisha	20.3	20.4	20.5	21.2	20.9	21.3	21.7	21.6	22.2	22.8	22.5	22.5
16	Punjab	21.2	21.8	21.6	21.7	21.7	22.2	22.4	22.8	22.5	22.9	23.1	22.8
17	Rajasthan	19.9	19.5	19.5	19.4	19.5	20.1	21.6	20.6	21.1	21.2	22.1	21.7
18	Tamil Nadu	21.7	21.5	21.7	21.8	21.8	22	22.6	22.5	22.9	23.3	23.0	23.1
19	Uttar Pradesh	20.0	20.0	20.4	20.0	20.7	20.6	22.2	22.0	22.0	21.7	22.5	22.1
20	West Bengal	19.4	19.6	19.5	19.3	19.7	19.7	21.5	22.1	22.0	21.8	22.1	22.3

NEED FOR FAMILY PLANNING

Women of reproductive age can benefit from preconception care. Its set of interventions is designed to identify and reduce risk of women's health and improve pregnancy outcomes through prevention and management of health conditions. Unintended pregnancies are associated with many negative health consequences which include pregnancies that are unwanted. Healthy timing and spacing of pregnancies has positive effects on maternal health and new born outcomes. Women who have their issues at 27 to 32 month intervals are more likely to avoid anemia and bleeding. Many women fear the side effects of contraceptive methods, having experienced some side effects themselves. Others fear their husband's displeasure if they use family planning or they oppose for personal reasons. In rural Karnataka currently married women are facing the problem of unmet need for family planning. 6.6 per cent of rural women and 5 per cent of urban women are facing the problem of unmet family planning. The highest percentage of unmet needs for family planning was noted in the age group 15-19 years. Unmet need for contraception can lead to unintended pregnancies, which pose risks for women, their families, and societies.

Table 5 Need for family planning

Background characteristic	Unmet need for family planning		Met need for family planning (currently using)		Total demand for family planning	
	For spacing	For limiting	For spacing	For limiting	For spacing	For limiting
Age						
15-19	26.3	2.0	2.4	4.3	28.7	6.3
20-24	13.3	5.4	4.0	35.9	17.3	41.3
25-29	6.0	4.4	3.2	62.4	9.2	66.9
30-34	2.8	5.4	1.3	75.3	4.1	80.8
35-39	0.4	2.3	0.1	78.6	0.6	80.9
40-44	0.0	1.5	0.2	78.4	0.2	79.9
45-49	0.0	0.6	0.0	76.2	0.0	76.8
Residence						
Urban	5.1	4.8	3.4	57.4	8.5	62.2
Rural	6.6	2.8	0.8	64.6	7.4	67.4
Education						
No education	3.4	2.8	0.2	69.6	3.5	72.3
<5 years complete	3.5	2.4	0.2	69.9	3.8	72.3
5-9 years complete	8.7	3.8	2.0	58.8	10.8	62.7
10 or more years complete	8.1	5.3	5.2	48.2	13.3	53.5

Religion						
Hindu	5.9	3.2	1.7	63.0	7.6	66.2
Muslim	5.7	6.7	2.5	53.7	8.3	60.3
Christian	10.3	7.4	4.8	49.3	15.2	56.7
Others	4.7	0.0	0.0	67.8	4.7	67.8
Caste/tribes						
Scheduled castes	5.9	3.7	0.9	64.4	6.8	68.1
Scheduled tribes	4.2	1.1	1.1	60.3	5.3	61.4
Other backward class	6.2	3.8	1.8	60.6	8.0	64.4
Others	6.5	4.0	3.1	60.2	9.6	64.2
Wealth index						
Lowest	6.4	4.4	0.0	56.2	6.4	60.7
Second	5.6	2.6	0.3	66.0	5.9	68.6
Middle	6.4	3.1	1.0	65.6	7.4	68.7
Fourth	6.7	3.8	2.4	60.1	9.1	63.9
Highest	4.9	4.6	4.6	57.4	9.5	62.0

Source: NFHS-3, 2005-06

ANTENATAL CARE

Antenatal care is an important determinant of high maternal mortality rate and one of the basic components of maternal care on which the life of mothers and babies depend. Antenatal care can be defined as; women can access antenatal care services either by visiting a help centre where such services are available or from health workers during their visits. One of the most important components of antenatal care is to offer information and advice to women about pregnancy related complications. Further antenatal visits may raise awareness about the need for care during delivery. While antenatal care is considered essential for the health both the mother and the child. NFHS-III reports that a large majority of urban women received antenatal checkups from doctors. Antenatal checkup services are slightly higher for births to Christians than Hindus and Muslims. The consumption of antenatal checkup services is lower for births to women living in rural areas, women from scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. In India, the shorter distances to antenatal care services and the virtual relieve of travelling in urban areas, as well as the higher educational attainment of women, could be important factors for the higher proportion of check-ups received by women in urban areas than in rural areas(Table 6).

Table 6 Antenatal Care

Background characteristic	Doctor	ANM/nurse midwife/ LHV	Other health personnel	Dai/TBA	Anganwadi/ ICDS worker	Other
Age at birth						
<20	72.7	16.8	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.3
20-34	80.7	7.9	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.3
35-49	82.4	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Birth order						
1	87.7	8.3	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.2
2-3	79.0	9.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.3
4+	60.7	12.8	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.4
Residence						
Urban	90.4	3.8	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.0
Rural	71.9	13.2	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5
Education						
No education	57.3	15.5	0.8	1.2	0.8	0.4
<5 years complete	75.3	14.4	0.0	0.8	0.8	0.0
5-9 years complete	88.8	7.3	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.4
10 or more years complete	93.5	4.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Religion						
Hindu	77.6	10.1	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.4
Muslim	86.3	6.9	1.1	0.0	0.6	0.0
Christian	92.3	7.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Caste/tribes						
Scheduled castes	71.6	13.1	0.4	0.0	0.4	14.1
Scheduled tribes	59.6	18.5	0.0	2.5	1.6	17.9
Other backward class	82.1	7.9	0.4	0.6	0.3	7.9
Others	85.7	7.3	0.4	0.0	0.4	5.6
Wealth index						
Lowest	57.0	11.9	0.0	2.1	1.0	27.4
Second	65.0	16.3	0.9	0.6	0.6	16.1
Middle	76.3	12.5	0.3	0.3	0.8	8.5
Fourth	89.9	6.8	0.5	0.2	0.0	2.3
Highest	98.2	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1

ANM= Auxiliary nurse midwife, LHV= Lady health visitor, TBA= Traditional birth attendant, ICDS= Integrated Child Development Services.

Source: NFHS-3, 2005-06

PLACE OF DELIVERY & ASSISTANCE DURING DELIVERY

Insufficient counseling during antenatal visits is the main cause for low delivery in health facility. Minimum time used by health workers for counseling pregnant mothers during

antenatal clinic is the missed opportunity to educate women importance of health facilities delivery. In some places providers are not informing pregnant mothers the meaning of expected date of delivery and when the labour pain start early before that date they end up delivering in their homes even if they were interested to deliver in health facilities. And also mother's literacy level is important determinant of place of delivery as those with less education tend to deliver at home, and those educated tend to give birth's in health facilities. Unreliable transport is also is a barrier to access skilled delivery in rural areas, failure to plan in advance for transport cause higher number of women to deliver in their homes even if they had planned to deliver in health facilities. In Karnataka, majority of urban women (72%) had received delivery assistance from a doctor, whereas only 46 per cent rural women were received delivery assistance from doctor. More births took place in private sector (43%) than in public sector. In rural Karnataka traditional birth attendant still play an important role in deliveries. Traditional birth attendants are useful in the maternal health system, but there will not be a substantial reduction in maternal mortality by deliveries conducted through traditional birth attendants.

Table 1.7 Place of delivery & Assistance during delivery

Place of delivery & Assistance during delivery	Urban	Rural
Place of delivery		
Health facility	81.8	54.8
Public sector	37.8	33.0
NGO/ trust	0.9	1.1
Private sector	43.0	20.6
At home	17.8	44.7
Own home	9.6	24.9
Parents home	8.1	18.7
Other home	0.1	1.1
Other	0.4	0.5
Assistance during delivery		
Doctor	72.0	46.0
ANM/nurse/midwife/LHV	12.1	14.3
Other health personnel	0.4	0.8
Dai (TBA)	4.9	14.4
Friends/ relatives	10.1	23.4
Percentage delivered by a skilled provider	84.5	61.0
Percentage delivered by caesarean section	22.2	11.6
Number of births	802	1,378
ANM= Auxiliary nurse midwife, LHV= Lady health visitor, TBA= Traditional birth attendant.		

Source: NFHS-3, 2005-06

MATERNAL MORTALITY RATIO

Maternal and child mortality are two critical indicators that measures not only health conditions, but overall development level of a country. Pregnancy related and infant deaths in the country have declined from few years earlier. According to the latest data released by Registrar general of India, India's maternal mortality rate or the rate of deaths among women during or after pregnancy, declined by 16% in 2011-12 from 2007-09. Government of India has taken many steps for the improvement of health of pregnant and nursing women and women in reproductive age group. But, the result is not satisfactory enough as far as the maternal mortality ratio is considered. Early age of marriage among women, early age of pregnancy, high birth rates and less spacing between two deliveries are some social factors which cause in increase in maternal mortality ratio. In is scary that among south Indian states, maternal mortality highest (178) in Karnataka and lowest in Kerala (81).

Table 1.8 Maternal Mortality Ratio in some states

MATERNAL MORTALITY RATIO (PER 1,00,000 LIVE BIRTHS)					
India/States	1997-1998	1999-2001	2001-2003	2004-2006	2006-2007
India	398	327	301	254	212
Andhra Pradesh	197	220	195	154	134
Assam	568	398	490	480	390
Bihar/Jharkhand	531	400	371	312	261
Gujarat	46	202	172	160	148
Haryana	136	176	162	186	153
Karnataka	245	266	228	213	178
Kerala	150	149	110	95	81
Madhya Pradesh/ Chhattisgarh	441	407	379	335	269
Maharashtra	166	169	149	130	104
Odisha	346	424	358	303	258
Punjab	280	177	178	192	172
Rajasthan	508	501	445	388	318
Tamil Nadu	131	167	134	111	97
Uttar Pradesh/Uttarakhand	606	539	517	440	359
West Bengal	303	218	194	141	145

Source: Registrar General of India, Ministry of Home Affairs (SRS Estimates)

CONCLUSION:

From the preceding analysis we can wrap up that the overall reproductive health status of rural women in Karnataka is half empty and half full. For that reason a mindful effort is necessary to improve and implement the policies and programmes of overall reproductive health of women in general and rural women in particular. A substantial proportion of the overall health problems of older women relate directly to pregnancy. A number of other health problems of both elderly men and women relate to unsafe sexual practice. These problems are almost may be preventable. They result from a lack of adequate services for education, contraception, safe pregnancy and delivery, safe abortion, and the like. These service inadequacies have effect ill health and death which extend far beyond the reproductive years. Pregnancies and safe sex are important contributors to later reproductive health or ill health, but they are not the only ones, diseases and other problems of the reproductive system, from cancers to impotence, also require attention. Then only maternal health can be safeguarded and shielded.

REFERENCES

1. Goel S.L. (2004), *Health care Policies and Programmes*, Deep and Deep, New Delhi P-198-199.
2. *Health and Family Welfare Statistics in India* (2013), Ministry of Health and Family welfare, Government of India, New Delhi.
3. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS), 2010. *District Level Household and Facility Survey (DLHS-3), 2007-08:India. Karnataka*: Mumbai: IIPS.
4. Koenig A. Michael (2008) *Reproductive health in India*, Rawat, Jaipur.
5. *National Family Health Survey, 2005-2006*, IIPS, Mumbai.
6. *The World's Women* (2010), United Nations, New York, 2010

Details of Authors :

1. Dr. Shravana Gad
Teaching Faculty
Department of Women's Studies and Sociology
Karnatak University, Pavatenagar, Dharwad 580003
Karnataka, India.

2. Dr. Shaukath Azim
Senior Professor of Sociology
Karnatak University, Pavatenagar, Dharwad 580003
Karnataka, India.